

Survey on Refactoring for Elixir

FREE AND ENLIGHTENED CONSENT

Title: Refactorings for systems implemented in the Elixir functional language

Institution: DCC / ICEx / UFMG

Responsible researchers:

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Associate professor at the Department of Computer Science at UFMG

This "Free and Enlightened Consent" contains information about our research. If you have any questions, do not hesitate to ask the responsible researchers.

Evaluation goals: This study aims to understand the main refactoring strategies used in code implemented in the Elixir functional language

Survey information: We will ask you questions about your demographics, positions held, experience with Elixir, and your perception about the refactoring strategies in Elixir (use frequency and impact on system quality)

Data collection and use: The data will be collected through this Google Form. It is estimated that each participant will need a maximum of 20 minutes to complete the answers. This data will be used to promote good practices to improve the quality of code implemented in Elixir. The identities of all participants, as well as their responses, will be kept confidential. You may choose to receive the preliminary results of the study, with the anonymity of data and participants preserved. The results will be published and presented at conferences and scientific journals without revealing the identity of the participants.

If you decide not to participate in the research: You are free to refuse to participate or withdraw your consent at any time. Your decision will not affect any relationship with the evaluators, professors, or the institution responsible for this research.

Compensation: Your participation is voluntary and unpaid. In addition, you will not be charged for participating in this research.

If you have any problems or any other questions about the research: You can contact Lucas Vegi at any time at lucasvegi@dcc.ufmg.br.

If you have questions about the ethical aspects of this research: Contact the Research Ethics Committee of the Federal University of Minas Gerais (COEP-UFMG). Address: Av. Antônio Carlos, 6627. Administrative Unit II – 2nd floor - Room 2005. Pampulha Campus. Belo Horizonte – MG, Brazil. CEP: 31270-901. E-mail: coep@prpq.ufmg.br. Phone: +55 (31) 3409-4592. Opening hours: 09:00 AM to 11:00 AM; 02:00 PM to 04:00 PM (UTC-3).

Risks and measures to minimize them: When answering the questions, you may feel uncomfortable with questions that can bring back bad memories, fear of not knowing the answer, or even being identified. If you feel uncomfortable, you can pause completing the questionnaire and withdraw from participation at any time. The guarantee of data confidentiality ensured by the researchers is limited to the privacy policies of the virtual environment used for data collection (Google Forms). According to Brazilian legislation (Art. 9 of Resolution nº 510/16 of the National Health Council), in case of any damages resulting from your participation in this research, you will have the right to be compensated, under the terms of the Law.

Benefits: This research aims to promote good practices for improving the quality of systems implemented in Elixir, thus justifying its risks.

This survey will be carried out entirely remotely. In this way, [this consent term will be made available in digital copy through this Google Form](#). A copy of this digital consent will be kept by the responsible researchers and you will receive a digital copy via email after signing the term.

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

E-mail *

Seu e-mail

Free and Enlightened Consent (voluntary agreement) *

I declare that I have read the document mentioned above and that I agree to participate as a volunteer, authorizing the anonymous use of the data generated by my participation for the academic purposes described above.

Your full name: *

Sua resposta

Próxima

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Survey on Refactoring for Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Demographic questions

How many different projects have you participated in using Elixir? *

- Only one project
- Between 2 and 4 projects
- More than 4 projects

Select your country: *

Elixir experience time: *

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- More than 3 years

Your city: *

Sua resposta

Voltar

Próxima

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Survey on Refactoring for Elixir

Perceptions on the Relevance and Prevalence of refactorings

Refactoring strategies are code transformations that do not alter a program's behavior. In our research, we aim to catalog and document refactorings for the Elixir programming language. We would like to know your perception regarding these refactorings.

Therefore, based on your experience, answer the questions below.

[Prevalence] How often do you perform this refactoring in your Elixir systems or see this refactoring being carried out in code implemented with this language?
(1 = it is very rare; 5 = it is very common)

[Relevance] How relevant is this refactoring in Elixir systems? (i.e., when answering consider the potential of this refactoring to have a positive impact on maintainability, comprehensibility, and evolution of Elixir code)
(1 = very low impact and relevance; 5 = high impact and relevance)

Notes:

- Each refactoring is accompanied by a short description and a link containing code examples;
- You don't have to answer all questions items if you don't want to.

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Grouping parameters in tuple]**.

This refactoring aims to group a number of a function's sequential and related parameters into a *tuple*, thereby shortening the list of parameters. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Extract function]**.

This refactoring aims to extract a code block from a function and create a new function with the extracted code, giving it a name that clearly explains its purpose. In the original function, the extracted code block is replaced by a call to the new function. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Splitting a large module]**.

This refactoring aims to split a large module (i.e., without a single responsibility) into several new ones, moving to each new module only the attributes and functions with purposes related to their respective responsibilities. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Pipeline using "with"]**.

This refactoring aims to replace the nested use of conditional statements (e.g., "if...else" and "case") to control a sequence of function calls, with a kind of pipeline using a "with" statement. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Function clauses to/from case clauses]**.

This refactoring restructures functions that use the divide-and-conquer pattern, making parallelization easier. To achieve this, it transforms a multi-clause function into a single-clause function, mapping function clauses into clauses of a "case" statement. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Transform "if" statements using pattern matching into a "case"]**.

When the result of pattern matching is crucial to define the execution flow of a code, it is recommended to use a "case" statement instead of an "if". Therefore, this refactoring aims to transform an "if" statement that uses pattern matching in a conditional check into a "case" statement. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Introduce processes]**.

This refactoring aims to introduce new concurrent processes to achieve a more optimal mapping between parallel processes and parallel activities of the problem being solved. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Replace function call with raw value in a pipeline start]**.

This refactoring aims to change the beginning of a pipeline (i.e., sequence of |>), extracting the initial parameter from the function call that originally starts the pipe and incorporating this value at the pipeline's start. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Remove single pipe]**.

This refactoring aims to replace a pipe that doesn't involve multiple chained function calls (i.e., those that have only two members, with the first being a variable or a zero-arity function, followed by a non-zero-arity function call), with a call to the function that was originally the last pipe member. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Closure conversion]**.

This refactoring transforms closures (i.e., anonymous functions that access variables outside their scope) into functions that receive the referenced variables as parameters. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Turning anonymous into local functions]**.

This refactoring (a.k.a. lambda lifting) aims to transform identical anonymous functions defined at different points in the codebase (i.e., duplicated code) into a single local function. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Struct field access elimination]**.

This refactoring aims to replace direct access to fields of a struct with the use of temporary variables that hold values extracted from these fields. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Register a process]**.

This refactoring aims to assign a user-defined name to a process ID and use that name instead of the process ID in messages exchanged between processes. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Inline function]**.

In some cases, a function's body just delegates to another function's call. In these situations, this refactoring replaces all calls to the function with its body and removes the function. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Struct guard to matching]**.

This refactoring aims to transform calls to `is_struct/1` or `is_struct/2` contained in guards clauses, into explicit pattern matching usage. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Explicit a double boolean negation]**.

In Elixir, when we perform a double boolean negation in a value, this will return `false` for `false` and `nil` values, and `true` for anything else. This refactoring aims to replace a double boolean negation with a new helper multi-clause function, improving code readability. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Replace conditional with polymorphism via Protocols]**.

This refactoring transforms a module that has a function with conditionals based on data types into a *Protocol* that defines the interface for this function. Furthermore, each data type previously handled in the conditionals is converted into a specific implementation of the *Protocol*. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

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* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Final remarks

Do you want to receive the preliminary results of this study? *

Yes

No

Please add here any comment about our work and survey:

Sua resposta

Uma cópia das suas respostas será enviada para o endereço de e-mail fornecido

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